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A STRUCTURAL EQUATION APPROACH TO INVESTIGATE DIFFERENT CONSTRUCTS OF PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Many engineering students experience difficulties in their professional career orientation as a result of the large number of career options presented in the broad engineering field. This has been linked to a hampered school-to-work transition and difficulties in career decision-making. Successful stimulation of a professional identity can be achieved by providing career guidance that aims to promote several key constructs underlying identity development, including *career exploration*, *awareness*, and *confidence*. This provides students with both a vocational and self-sense that prepares them better for their future career. Previous researchers often focused on a restricted set of underlying constructs, mostly in non-engineering students. This study overcomes these limitations with an in-depth analysis that examines five constructs simultaneously to contribute to a more general view of professional identity. By using structural equation modeling on the survey data, we aim to provide insights in the overall interplay of the constructs in the specific context of 624 Belgian engineering students at KU Leuven. We determine correlations between constructs and examine how these constructs differ for several personal variables. Results indicate substantial interconstruct correlations with construct differences for the phase of study, vocational

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interest, engineering persistence, and a small effect for parental occupation, but no effects for gender. These results contribute to a more general understanding of the professional identity of engineering students and the implications for career guidance during their education.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deciding on a future career is considered one of the most important decisions students have to make [1]. However, engineering students often experience difficulties in this process. Several problems have been linked to this difficult orientation. First, some engineering students lack an understanding of the engineering profession or what it requires to be an engineer, and are not aware of the myriad career options [2]. Second, the engineering education seems to show a low cohesion with the professional world as student's values, skills and expectations do not always align with practice. These problems hamper their career orientation and their transition from academia to the engineering world [3].

The development of a professional identity can support the career orientation. Developing such an identity is the fundamental aim of educational career guidance [4], thereby facilitating the professional transition. In this process, a good understanding of the professional engineering identity is required, along with the needs of the engineering students.

When focusing on identity research in engineering education, several limitations in the current body of literature are observed [5]. First, research on professional identity in engineering is scarce. Earlier research mainly focused on non-engineering students. Second, professional identity is considered a multifaceted concept. However, most studies have focused on specific aspects of professional identity which hindered to fully understand its broad scope. The purpose of this study is to provide a more comprehensive view on the professional identity of engineering students. Improving its understanding can contribute to essential career guidance.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Professional identity: a multiconstruct concept

In the process of professional identity development, students gain personal and vocational knowledge that allows them to identify their abilities, interests and aspirations and let them align these with the vocational possibilities and their required competencies [4]. An important aspect of professional identity for career guidance is its multifaceted characteristic. Namely, it is widely recognized that professional identity development is guided by several underlying constructs, including *career exploration*, *career awareness*, and *career confidence*, among others. (1) *Career exploration* reflects the behaviors associated with the information gathering to build one's vocational knowledge [6]. (2) *Career awareness* shows one's knowledge and understanding of the vocational possibilities and the associated competencies [7]. In this study, the construct of *career awareness* was operationalised by *professional roles awareness* and *competence awareness*, which has proven relevance before [8]. These constructs are based on Craps *et al.* (2021) who developed a competency

based professional role model for future engineers comprising product leadership (focus on radical innovation), operational excellence (focus on process and product optimisation) and customer intimacy (focus on client tailored solutions), and their required non-technical competencies [9]. (3) *Career confidence*, here again conceptualized as *professional role confidence*, covers two subconstructs as reported by Cech *et al.* (2011): *role-fit confidence* and *competence confidence*, referring to the confidence that a professional engineering role corresponds to one's interests and values, and the confidence in one's skills required for that role [10].

2.2 Professional identity differs over personal factors

A second important aspect regarding professional identity is that construct differences exist between students regarding multiple personal factors such as their socio-economic status [11], phase of study [12], family support [13], gender [14,15], or persistence in an engineering career [10]. However, these factors have been mostly identified throughout studies with non-engineering students.

2.3 Professional identity and career guidance

Both the construct associations and the personal variables affect the implementation of educational career guidance. First, career guidance programmes can be designed to specifically focus on desired aspects of professional identity. Second, the presence of personal factors clarify that guidance can vary according to the needs of the corresponding target group. Such adequate career guidance for engineering students relies on a clear understanding of their professional identity.

3 AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aims to contribute to the comprehensive understanding of professional identity in engineering education by simultaneously focusing on multiple identity constructs within the same cohort of students. Our research focus is to, first, examine the association structure between the constructs, and second, determine construct differences for five personal variables, i.e. gender, parental occupation, the phase of study, vocational interest, and persistence in engineering careers using structural equation modeling techniques. In the final section, we discuss some supportive insights for educational career guidance.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Participants

Survey data was collected from 624 engineering students of the Faculty of Engineering Technology at KU Leuven in Belgium. Participants were predominantly male (85% vs 15%), which corresponds with the university's engineering population. All possible phases of study were included: first bachelor year (32%), second bachelor year (22%), third bachelor year (23%), the master year (17%), and a transfer programme prior to the Master's programme for graduates of technical University College (6%). Ethical approval was sought and obtained for this study from our university's Ethics Committee (G-2019 03 1596) and participants have consented to be part of this

research. They were informed that their participation was voluntary and that the analysis would be conducted anonymously.

4.2 Survey

Data was collected cross-sectionally via a 10-minute electronic survey using Qualtrics. Students participated in May 2019 or 2020. In a first part of the survey, five sets of Likert scale questions were implemented, each probing the student's attitude towards one of the five professional identity constructs: (1) *Career exploration* (8 questions, Cronbach's alpha: 0.83) probed the extend of different information seeking behaviors (e.g. "I go to job fairs or company events"). (2) *Professional roles awareness* (3 questions, Cronbach's alpha: 0.57) probed their understanding of the professional engineering roles (e.g. "I understand the description of the engineering roles"). (3) *Competence awareness* (4 questions, Cronbach's alpha: 0.52) probed their understanding of the competencies associated with the professional engineering roles (e.g. "I recognize most of the competencies in the professional roles model"). (4) *Role-fit confidence* (6 questions, Cronbach's alpha: 0.75) probed the confidence towards their desired engineering role (e.g. "The engineering role I chose is the most suitable one for me"). (5) *Competence confidence* (4 questions, Cronbach's alpha: 0.53) probed the confidence in their non-technical skills (e.g. "I possess the required non-technical competencies to grow in this engineering role"). This, and *role-fit confidence*, was based on the survey of Cech *et al.* (2011).

In a second part, the following background information was collected for five personal variables. One survey question indicated whether the student could identify with one or a combination of the professional engineering roles as developed by Craps *et al.* (2021) ('yes': 84%, 'no': 16%), this variable is referred to as vocational interest. Other questions asked whether one of the parents was an engineer ('yes': 29%, 'no': 71%), or whether the student considered another job outside engineering ('yes': 16%, 'no': 37%, 'sometimes': 47%), which represent parental occupation and engineering persistence respectively. Gender information and the phase of study were provided by the university.

4.3 Statistical analysis

The constructs were operationalized according to the exploratory factor model developed by De Boever *et al.* (2021) [16]. First, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was employed to validate this factor model, and second, construct differences were examined for five personal variables using structural equation modeling (SEM). This was performed by including the variables gender, parental occupation, phase of study, vocational interest, and engineering persistence in the CFA model. Both the CFA and SEM used 20 multiply imputed datasets to account for missingness, which maximally amounted 15% in the survey. The model fit was assessed using the averaged model fit indices for the comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA), and standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR). Values above 0.90 for CFI and TLI, and values below 0.08 for RMSEA and SRMR signified a well-fitting model [17]. Ordinal categorical CFA and SEM were used because of the categorical nature of the Likert scales, which employed

polychoric correlations and the diagonally weighted least squares (DWLS) estimator. Reported factor loadings were obtained using standardized factors only, which for categorical variables in the SEM indicate the difference in standardized construct level for a respective group compared to the reference group. The mice package [18] in Rstudio was used for multiple imputation, and the semTools package [19] was used to perform the CFA and SEM on the multiply imputed data.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Professional identity constructs are considerably correlated

Based on unsatisfactory modification indices exceeding a value of 20, three error correlations were introduced in the CFA model between survey items with linguistic similarities, which improved the model with an adequate fit (initial vs final: CFI=0.955 vs 0.972, TLI=0.949 vs 0.968, RMSEA=0.057 vs 0.046, SRMR=0.065 vs 0.058) and appropriate factor loadings (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Final CFA model. Factor correlations and correlated errors are presented by the double-headed arrows between the constructs (ovals) and items (rectangles) respectively. Significance levels are indicated with asterisks ($0.05 > * \geq 0.01 > ** \geq 0.001 > ***$).

From the final CFA model (Figure 1), all correlations between the constructs show significant positive values between 0.28 and 0.60. This suggests both an appropriate discriminant validity between the constructs, and substantial interconstruct associations. Higher levels in one construct are thus related to higher levels in another construct. The largest interconstruct correlations were observed between *professional roles awareness* and *competence awareness*, and *competence awareness* and *competence confidence*. The associations with the two confidence constructs, i.e. *role-fit confidence* and *competence confidence*, were different for *career exploration*, and *professional roles* and *competence awareness*, while the associations for *career exploration* with the awareness constructs were similar.

5.2 Professional identity constructs show differences for multiple variables

Construct differences were examined for five variables, i.e. parental occupation, gender, engineering persistence, phase of study, and vocational interest. This model had an acceptable fit (CFI=0.938, TLI=0.958, RMSEA=0.047, SRMR=0.062). The

results are comprised in Figure 2, showing the significant construct differences between the variable's categories and their respective reference category.

Figure 2. SEM. Reference categories are 'no' (engineering persistence, middle bottom row), the master year (phase of study), female (gender), 'not an engineer' (parental occupation), 'no' (vocational interest). The measurement model in Figure 1 was used to determine the constructs, which was omitted here in the visualization for clarity, and only significant effects are shown.

2.2.1 Parental occupation

The professional identity of engineering students did not seem to be influenced substantially by whether one of their parents was an engineer or not, as only a weak effect was observed for *career exploration*. This effect indicated a slightly increased level of *career exploration* when at least one of the parents was an engineer.

2.2.2 Gender

No differences between males and females were noted for any of the constructs, suggesting a similar professional identity.

2.2.3 Phase of study

Multiple effects were noted for the bachelor years regarding all constructs. *Career exploration* was reduced for students in the first, second and third bachelor year compared to the master year. The increasing loadings over the later bachelor years might suggest that *career exploration* increases when progressing the programme. Similarly, *competence confidence* seems to increase over the three bachelor years. On the other hand, only first and second year students showed decreased levels for *professional roles* and *competence awareness*, while *role-fit confidence* was decreased for second and third year students compared to master students. Finally, transfer students and master students showed similar construct levels, with the exception of *career exploration*, which was reduced in transfer students.

2.2.4 Vocational interest

Whether students were able to identify with a professional engineering role (vocational interest) was independent of considering another job outside engineering (engineering persistence) ($p=0.92$, $\chi^2=0.175$, $df=2$). Students that could identify with an engineering role showed higher levels for all constructs except *career exploration*, with the largest increase noted for *role-fit confidence*. Further exploration did not demonstrate clear differences between professional roles.

2.2.5 Engineering persistence

Students who were considering another job outside engineering showed lower *role-fit confidence* compared to students who were aiming for an engineering career. No differences were noted in *career exploration*, *competence confidence*, and *competence awareness*. However, a borderline insignificant effect was present for *professional roles awareness* ($p=0.054$, loading=-0.289), suggesting a reduced understanding of the professional engineering roles for students that considered a non-engineering job. Additionally, students who were still undecided about the engineering field also showed lower *role-fit confidence*, with a difference that is markedly smaller than for the former group (-0.144 vs. -0.356). Borderline insignificant effects were also observed for *professional roles awareness* ($p=0.065$, loading=-0.215) and *career exploration* ($p=0.058$, loading=-0.106).

6 DISCUSSION

Developing a professional identity is fundamental in student's career orientation, making this an active research field providing essential implications for educational guidance programmes. The present research aimed to expand the understanding of the professional identity of engineering students, which is a research population that did not receive much attention yet. Using structural equation modeling techniques, we simultaneously examined distinct constructs that are associated with professional identity development in engineering students to provide an in-depth exploration of these constructs in the same cohort.

Our results rehighlight the general perception that professional identity is a complex and multifaceted concept. We first demonstrated a positive association structure between five constructs, which had not been reported before in the same cohort, providing an in-depth overview of the multifaceted aspect of professional identity. This circumvents potential extrapolation issues between different cohorts resulting from cultural or other differences [1,11]. These results suggest that the underlying identity structure in engineering students follows similar mechanisms as in other student populations since positive construct associations have also been reported for high school students and non-engineering students [11,20].

The second result identifies several personal factors for each construct. Results demonstrated construct differences for phase of study, which has been identified in previous studies as well [12]. Developmental differences during student's education have been explained before in light of increasing experience [21]. Our results support this belief since gradual construct changes are present over bachelor years that might

suggest increasing levels for most constructs. Interestingly, *professional roles awareness* seems to decrease slightly after the first bachelor year, which might result from the unrealistic expectations of first year students regarding the engineering field at the start of their education, as stated elsewhere [22]. On the other hand, no gender differences were noted, while before, STEM and engineering males have also demonstrated higher *role-fit* and *competence confidence* [14,15]. These different findings might result from methodological and cohort differences. Also only one effect was noted for parental occupation, i.e. on *career exploration*, despite that parental influences have been considered key in the developmental process [13]. However, those studies mainly focused on parental support instead of parental occupation. A study with German high school students did suggest a larger *career exploration* when the educational track corresponded to that of the parents [23], as suggested by our results. The low number of parental effects might suggest that having an engineering parent does not add substantially to the professional identity development after pursuing the engineering major. Finally, lower construct levels were noted for students who could not yet identify with an engineering role, or who were considering another job outside engineering. These vocational interest and engineering persistence variables have been of little focus so far in studies investigating construct differences. However, in agreement with our results, an association was observed before between *role-fit confidence* and engineering persistence in engineering students [10]. Additionally, the same study showed that *competence confidence* was indifferent for persistence, which is also consistent with our analysis. Further investigation of the other construct differences for vocational interest and engineering persistence might be relevant to understand their occurrence in students.

4.1 Implications for career guidance

Our results provide several implications for career guidance in engineering education. First, the positive association structure among the identity constructs suggests the possibility to stimulate specific constructs through other constructs. Second, the correlations in our analysis showed that stronger and weaker links are present, suggesting that putative stimulation effects might differ considerably between constructs. Third, the examination of personal factors suggests that students without a clear vocational interest could benefit from a broad guidance intervention.

4.2 Limitations and future research

Additional research is required to unravel the explicit directional influence of one construct on another, which is not captured in the reported correlations. This would provide insights on both the direct and indirect stimulation of one or more constructs by another, presenting a more effective way for developing career guidance. Also, the construct differences over the bachelor years in our cross-sectional data are only suggestive for construct evolutions during the programme. This should be further addressed in a future longitudinal study that follows construct changes in the same individuals over time to investigate the evolution in professional identity in engineering students.

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